

MUHAMMAD AMINKHOJA MUQIMI'S ACTIVITY IN POETRY

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One of such writers is Muhammad Aminkhoja Muqimi, who has a worthy place in the history of Uzbek literature. The poet was born in 1850 in Bekvachcha mahalla (now Muqimiy Street) of Kokand. His father was Mirzakhoja Mirfozil oglu, a baker, and his mother was Bibioysha Sayidolim Nodirshaykh's daughter. The role of the mother in the acquisition of poetic nature is invaluable. Because her *Don't hold back, look for my name, look for happiness.*

ABSTRACT

In 1950 the works of the poet were issued in Russian in Moscow under the name "Lyrics and satire". On the occasion of the 50th anniversary of his death in 1953 a number of studies were created about him and laid the foundation for his studies. H.Yagubov's "Uzbek poet Mukhimy", A.Olimjonov's "Muhammad Amin Mukhimy", H. Zaripov's "Muhammad Amin Mukhimy", H.Razzakov's books "Mukhimy and Zavkhy", a collection of articles" were published. This article covers the study of Mukhimy's life and activities in the textbooks of literature in the pre-Independence period.

mother had a great education and was very good at oral art. It is because of this woman that poetic talent develops in Muqimi. He wrote his first poem at the age of ten. Muqimi had five children and a third child.

Such a fierce struggle between Muqimi and the reactionary groups is evidenced by Muqimi's poem "Search":

If the king is lost, look for gado

Indeed, the period in which Muqimi lived was complex. Such a difficult period was marked by the colonization of Central Asia, including Tsarist Russia. Muqimi is a poet who came from among the common people and gave all his strength to this nation. At the same time, he made a worthy contribution to the renewal of literature by with his own potential and status⁵. He emerged as a fiery singer of the oppressed working people, the poor artisans, and the homeless peasants.

Collection of books by H. Yakubov "Uzbek poet Muqimiy", A. Olimjanov "Muhammad Amin Muqimiy", H. Zaripov

bringing to light the changes taking place in social life due to the Russian invasion. His poems were spread in different cities of Turkestan during his lifetime, and poets sang them to him. Muqimi was a scholar who wrote poems about the national liberation movement and created a school

and Muqimiy" published. A lot of research has been done on the works of the poet. Unfortunately, Muqimi's works were interpreted one-sidedly in accordance with the requirements of the Soviet ideology. As a result, the poet's poetic legacy was taken away from its essence. That is, his works

"Muhammad Amin Muqimiy", H. Razzakov "Muqimiy and Zavqiy" and articles "Furqat have been preserved in various manuscripts and lithographs, in the notebooks of artists, in the collections of amateur writers, in some pieces of paper in the hands of different people. Karimov's "Collection of Works" was published a total

were edited, shortened, and left in the sources. Muqimi's works of four times (1958,1960,1973,1974). Unfortunately, Muqimi's work was not fully and perfectly published in these publications due to the strong pressure of the communist ideology.

In current editions:

Dorig'o mulkimizning sohibi ahli sharor
o'lmish,
Shariat hukmi qozilar qo'lida purg'ubor
o'lmish,
Ba joyi amri ma'ruf kori munkar oshkor
o'lmish,
Hakim-u, olim-u,sohib fasohat xor-u zor
o'lmish,
Bu kunda kimki imonin sotar, ul e'tibor
o'lmish.

In fact:

Dorig'o, dini islom hokimi ahli kuffor
o'lmish,
Shariat ko'zqusikim kufr gardidin g'ubor
o'lmish,
Ba joyi amri ma'ruf nahyi munkar oshkor
o'lmish,
Sayid, sodotlar behurmat-u, ko'p xor-u zor
o'lmish,
Bu kunda kimki imonin sotibdur, e'tibor
o'lmish.

A comparison of the verses shows that the poem has been analyzed in a completely opposite way.

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